

Extending ISO 13485 Beyond Manufacturers: A Comprehensive Framework for the Entire Medical Device Lifecycle

Adamantios Ntanis ¹, Yuxin Zhou², Mariet Nouri Janian², and Alberto Sanna²

¹PD Neurotechnology Ltd, Quality and Regulatory Department, Ioannina, Greece

²IRCCS San Raffaele Hospital, Center for Advanced Technology in Health and Well-Being, Milan, Italy

March 17, 2026

ISO 13485:2016 is an internationally recognized standard that specifies requirements for establishing and maintaining a quality management system (QMS) in the medical device industry. It provides a structured framework to support manufacturers in consistently ensuring product quality, thereby enhancing patient safety, product effectiveness, and compliance with applicable regulatory requirements. However, its applicability to non-manufacturing stakeholders, such as integrators, operators, distributors, and service providers, remains limited. Drawing on insights from the NEMECYS Horizon Europe project, which implemented four diverse case studies spanning the full medical device lifecycle, this paper identifies key shortcomings in the standard's current scope and structure. These include gaps in addressing post-production activities, inter-stakeholder collaboration, and processes such as training, awareness, and decommissioning. We propose potential improvements, including clarifying target audiences, extending lifecycle coverage, and reorganizing requirements to meaningfully include non-manufacturers. By highlighting these limitations and suggesting enhancements, this work provides a framework for evolving ISO 13485:2016 into a more comprehensive standard applicable across the entire medical device ecosystem, thereby supporting consistent quality and safety for all stakeholders.

Keywords: ISO 13485; ISO 13485:2016; medical devices; quality management system; QMS; regulatory compliance.

1 Introduction

The medical devices industry is highly regulated, and for good reason. Beyond the undeniable risks to human life, the sector faces numerous serious concerns, including issues

related to privacy, ethics, and more. Alleviating these concerns requires the collaboration of multiple stakeholders across the industry, resulting in a complex, interconnected web of requirements for organizations with diverse backgrounds and areas of expertise. This is no easy task, as the needs and regulatory compliance requirements of a medical device manufacturer differ significantly from those of a third-party provider of distribution or maintenance services. Yet, significant cooperation is essential, as no stakeholder operates in isolation.

To guide the medical device industry, ISO 13485 was established, with the current version at the time of writing being ISO 13485:2016 [9]. It provides the de facto standard for establishing a quality management system (QMS) in organizations involved in one or more stages of a medical device’s lifecycle. As a requirements standard, it enables organizations to demonstrate conformance through an external audit, thereby verifying the implementation of all specified requirements. In its introduction, ISO 13485:2016 clearly states that it is intended for use by all medical device stakeholders, whether involved in one, several, or all stages of a device’s lifecycle, establishing requirements relevant to every participant. Stakeholders may include medical device manufacturers, suppliers of products or services, third-party distributors, providers of maintenance or servicing, or any other organization involved in the supply chain, from the design of a medical device, through its integration and operation, continuing with its servicing, and concluding with its decommissioning. This scope is further underscored in “ISO 13485:2016 – Medical Devices: A Practical Guide” [10].

Recognizing the importance of ISO 13485:2016, this work has three objectives. First, it demonstrates that while ISO 13485:2016 is an excellent standard for medical device manufacturers, its applicability is more limited for other stakeholders in the medical device ecosystem. Second, it identifies the specific limitations in the current version that hinder its broader applicability. Third, it proposes potential improvements, or more precisely, possible future extensions that can help the standard achieve its overarching current goals, acting as a foundation for adaptation to diverse stakeholder needs. The findings presented were derived from the implementation of a series of case studies conducted by a diverse group of medical device stakeholders within the NEMECYS Horizon Europe research project [14].

This work should also be understood in the context of the publication and revision history of the standard itself. The current version, ISO 13485:2016, is approaching its tenth year, a timeline that increasingly supports the case for systematic revision. While the standard maintains advantages in clarity and coherence relative to the interpretive complexities inherent in regional frameworks such as the MDD and MDR, the elapsed time since its release reinforces the importance of strategic updates to ensure alignment with current technological capabilities, organizational methodologies, and regulatory developments.

2 Context and Motivation

The limitations of ISO 13485:2016 discussed in this work emerged during the implementation of four medical device–related case studies conducted across two pilot rounds within the NEMECYS Horizon Europe project. The project focused on the cybersecurity of medical devices and included the systematic evaluation of relevant legal and regulatory documentation, such as cybersecurity standards and guidelines [1]. The identification of these limitations was neither a primary research objective nor an explicit aim of the project; rather, it arose as a secondary outcome of the work.

The execution of the case studies required close collaboration among a diverse group of medical device stakeholders, including manufacturers, integrators, and operators, while simultaneously addressing multiple regulatory compliance challenges. A central requirement of this collaboration was the establishment of a shared understanding of the medical device lifecycle, which served as a practical framework for organizing project activities and aligning stakeholder responsibilities. Two primary motivations for establishing a clear lifecycle are highlighted below:

Effective communication: Defining the entire lifecycle was essential for ensuring consistent and effective communication among stakeholders involved in its various stages. In many cases, the stages in which specific stakeholders participated were completely distinct from those of others, often with little or no overlap. Establishing a common understanding of the full lifecycle therefore provided a shared framework that facilitated clearer interaction and coordination across all participants.

Regulatory compliance: Regulatory compliance represented another key reason for defining the lifecycle. Within the NEMECYS project, assessing legal and regulatory documentation related to cybersecurity was an important task, and understanding the distinct stages of the lifecycle was crucial, as each stage is subject to specific regulatory requirements and corresponding guidance documents. Mapping these requirements to the appropriate lifecycle stages enabled a more systematic and efficient approach to compliance management.

In attempting to apply the lifecycle model defined in ISO 13485:2016, the practical limitations of the standard discussed in this work created friction among stakeholders, prompting a more thorough evaluation of the standard and the development of solutions to address these issues. The lifecycle defined by ISO 13485:2016 is illustrated in Figure 1. The stages shown, along with their associated processes and activities, are intended to convey the standard’s underlying concepts rather than provide an exact reproduction of its lifecycle phases. To enhance clarity, elements from the standard have been grouped and reorganized to emphasize the essential activities and concepts it describes.

In retrospect, the implementation of these case studies provided an ideal “playground” for exploring the boundaries of ISO 13485:2016 applicability, as well as a valuable opportunity to identify both issues and potential solutions. This was made possible by bringing together experts from multiple medical device–related industries, each contributing diverse experience and skills. For reference, the medical devices examined in

Figure 1: Lifecycle stages illustrating processes and activities that summarize the intent of ISO 13485:2016. They do not exactly reproduce the lifecycle stages or the processes and activities as stated in the standard.

the case studies spanned a broad range of hardware and software ecosystems, including components incorporating artificial intelligence, operating across multiple environments, and used by a variety of stakeholders such as healthcare professionals, patients, hospital technical personnel, and caregivers. The diversity of devices and users further amplified the regulatory and cybersecurity challenges encountered, providing the context in which the limitations of ISO 13485:2016 became evident. The case studies specifically focused on the manufacturing, integration, and operational processes of the following medical devices:

Wearable bioimpedance measurement patch: The Re:Balans [16] is a non-invasive wearable sensor designed to measure hydration levels in patients with fluid-management-related health conditions, such as individuals with end-stage renal disease requiring dialysis. The device wirelessly transmits data to an external unit, such as a smart tablet or IoT gateway, enabling continuous monitoring. Its purpose is to provide real-time feedback to both patients and healthcare providers, supporting more accurate fluid management and reducing the risk of related complications.

Wearable IMU-based monitoring devices: The PDMonitor [2] is a CE-marked Class IIa wearable medical device designed to continuously track and assess motor symptoms in people with Parkinson’s disease (PD). Using small sensors on the wrists, ankles, and waist, it collects detailed movement data, which is uploaded to a cloud platform. Patients can log medication and symptoms via a mobile app, while clinicians access objective reports through a web dashboard to monitor tremor, dyskinesia, gait disturbances, and other key symptoms. PDMonitor helps doctors make more informed treatment decisions by providing continuous, real-world insights into disease progression.

Figure 2: Structure of the implementation of the four medical device-related case studies across two pilots in the NEMECYS research project, covering the full medical device lifecycle from pre-production through production to post-production activities.

Diabetes management mobile application: This Class IIb Software as a Medical Device (SaMD) is a mobile application [18] designed to help people with diabetes manage their therapy more effectively, including monitoring glucose levels, tracking insulin intake, and providing personalized recommendations. The app uses a machine learning algorithm to optimize bolus and basal insulin doses based on patient-entered information, such as meals, blood glucose readings, and other relevant health data. By integrating real-time data with individualized guidance, the application supports safer, more precise diabetes management and helps patients make informed decisions about their therapy. It is developed to meet strict regulatory standards for medical software while ensuring usability and safety for patients.

In-vitro continuous glucose monitoring: The FreeStyle Libre 2 [4] is a continuous glucose monitoring system designed to help patients and healthcare professionals track glucose levels in real time. It consists of a sensor worn on the patient’s upper arm that continuously measures glucose, an Abbott reader that scans the sensor to display glucose values at home or in the hospital, and the FreeStyle LibreView web application, which allows healthcare professionals to access and analyze patient data. Together, these components provide a seamless way to monitor glucose trends, support informed treatment decisions, and improve diabetes management.

Figure 2 provides an overview of the structure of these case studies.

3 Structure Overview

In the medical device manufacturing industry, the standard explicitly links the processes and activities defined for each stage of the device lifecycle, as shown in Figure 1, to those

actually implemented during design and development. This alignment is expected, as compliance with the standard requires manufacturers to align their internal processes with its prescribed requirements. Consequently, despite variations in how individual organizations implement specific processes and activities, ISO 13485:2016 provides a common structural framework that supports consistency and facilitates effective communication among manufacturers. Although the standard is formally applicable to any organization within its defined scope in the medical device industry, its practical applicability remains limited. Some of these limitations appear to arise from the standard's structural design. While this design makes ISO 13485:2016 particularly well suited for manufacturers, it may also constrain broader applicability and contribute to gaps in coverage for other stakeholders and post-manufacturing stages.

ISO 13485:2016 is a management system standard (MSS) [11]. Management system standards must conform to the ISO High-Level Structure (HLS), now referred to as the Harmonized Structure [12], which prescribes a uniform sequence of clause numbers, clause titles, text structure, common terms, and core definitions. The High-Level Structure (HLS) is primarily designed to promote consistency among management system standards (MSS). Its purpose is to provide a unifying, harmonized framework that enhances the alignment and compatibility of these standards. The HLS is not intended to improve the clarity of individual ISO standards; rather, it allows organizations to add additional discipline-specific requirements as needed [15, 12]. At the time of writing, ISO 13485:2016 does not conform to the Harmonized Structure, even though this framework is mandatory for all ISO management system standards. Consequently, any major future revision of the standard will need to ensure compliance with the HLS [15].

Had ISO 13485:2016 adopted the HLS, it would have been required to use mandatory terminology and incorporate numerous prescriptive requirements, thereby reducing flexibility in addressing the standard's subject matter. As a result, the current structure can be advantageous for manufacturers, as it is specifically tailored to their needs. It provides a logical framework for establishing a QMS for medical device manufacturing, beginning with governance and planning, progressing through the processes and activities involved in product realization, and culminating in the evaluation and improvement of both the QMS and the medical devices it supports. While the current structure focuses on the stages in which manufacturers are directly involved, it provides limited consideration for other stakeholders. At the same time, even for manufacturers, the framework does not fully address all critical phases of a medical device's lifecycle, such as decommissioning and disposal, which remain significant responsibilities even when carried out by third parties.

To assess how the structure of ISO 13485:2016 influences its practical applicability, the following sections provide a structural analysis of the standard, focusing on how requirements are distributed across its clauses. Clauses 1 through 6 provide a largely generic management system foundation, whereas Clause 7 contains the majority of requirements specific to medical device activities. Accordingly, the analysis begins with Clause 7, which provides detailed requirements on all processes required for design, development, supply chain management, production, installation, and servicing, all under a single unifying focus: the development of the medical device. At first glance, this fo-

cus may appear ideal; however, observations from the implementation of the case studies indicate that Clause 7 addresses installation and servicing only from the manufacturer's perspective, thereby overlooking the broader scope of the standard as it applies to other stakeholders involved in these stages of the medical device lifecycle. This is evident not only from the content of the subclauses pertaining to installation and servicing, but also from the fact that these subclauses are grouped directly under Clause 7, titled "Product Realization", which focuses primarily on product realization activities. Can the current structure of the document truly support the scope defined in its introduction if the bulk of the content is grouped under product realization? From a critical perspective, it is worth asking whether a third-party provider of installation or servicing services should be expected to comply with the existing requirements in the standard, given that these requirements are clearly targeted toward manufacturers.

Following Clause 7 on product realization, Clause 8 addresses evaluation and improvement and effectively concludes the standard. Although the introduction acknowledges that the standard may also be relevant for non-manufacturing organizations, including those involved in distribution, storage, decommissioning, and disposal, the requirements beyond product realization provide little guidance on the processes and activities relevant to these stakeholders. It is understandable that a standard must be relatively generic to accommodate the needs of various organizations. However, certain post-manufacturing stages, such as decommissioning and disposal, may constitute the full responsibility of some organizations seeking compliance with the standard and clearly fall within its intended scope, as noted in the introduction. Despite this, few, if any, requirements are provided for these stages, raising the question of what certification against the standard would actually signify for these organizations. It is important to note that this point also applies to manufacturers, as such post-manufacturing responsibilities may be part of their operations. As a result, even for manufacturers, where ISO 13485:2016 generally performs well, gaps remain in the standard's coverage.

4 Identified Limitations

During the pilot studies, the processes and activities of medical device integrators and operators could not be systematically mapped onto the lifecycle defined by the standard, nor clearly aligned with its prescribed processes and activities. This revealed specific limitations of the current ISO 13485:2016, particularly in covering the full device lifecycle, addressing critical processes, and accounting for the roles and interactions of all relevant stakeholders. More specifically:

Incomplete lifecycle representation: While the standard is intended to address the full lifecycle of a medical device, requirements related to integration, operation, and other post-manufacturing stages are largely missing in practice. In other words, guidance for the lifecycle of a medical device after it leaves the factory is largely absent. This issue concerns entire stages of the medical device lifecycle, rather than specific processes that might be missing within an already addressed stage. As a result, this limitation reduces the standard's applicability for organizations

involved in these later stages and highlights the need for a lifecycle-oriented framework that clearly defines all relevant processes and stakeholder responsibilities. Even with future updates, certain requirements would still not fit neatly within the lifecycle as currently defined in Figure 1, further illustrating the gaps in the standard's coverage.

Neglected processes and activities: The standard does not adequately address several important processes and activities that are essential for ensuring the safe and effective use of medical devices. Notably, training and awareness for users, including technical staff, healthcare personnel, and end-users such as patients, are entirely absent, despite their critical role in device safety and proper operation. Processes related to the decommissioning of medical devices are also largely missing, creating gaps in the management of devices at the end of their lifecycle. Although the final decommissioning and disposal of medical devices is mentioned in the introduction of the standard, no requirements are provided on the associated processes or activities, even though these steps are an integral part of the medical device lifecycle. Unlike the broader lifecycle gaps discussed previously, these missing processes could be incorporated into future updates within the current lifecycle framework shown in Figure 1, highlighting specific areas where the standard's coverage remains incomplete.

Compliance of non-manufacturers: The standard addresses non-manufacturing organizations, but the specific requirements applicable to them are often unclear. For example, it is not specified which requirements should apply to third-party installation and servicing providers. Currently, these activities are covered under the product realization clause, which is primarily targeted at manufacturers, although the standard does acknowledge cases in which the installation provider may be a third-party organization. This issue is also noted in the literature [3], where secondary stakeholders in the medical device sector, in the case of the study, researchers and clinical investigators in EU academic institutions, face challenges with so-called "traditional" QMS based on ISO 13485. The authors observe that such QMS are primarily designed for manufacturers, which makes implementation and compliance more difficult for these secondary stakeholders. The significance of compliance for non-manufacturers is further highlighted in [3], where regulatory frameworks such as the Medical Device Regulation (MDR) [6] effectively require a QMS for less conventional stakeholders, including researchers and clinical investigators. A key issue noted by the authors is that the MDR extends coverage to the initial phases of pre-clinical research, in contrast to the preceding Medical Device Directive (MDD) [5].

Role of operators: The standard does not explicitly address the role of medical device operators, despite their central importance throughout the device lifecycle. Clauses of the standard, such as 7.2.1, 8.2.1, 8.2.2, and 8.2.3, indirectly require continuous cooperation between manufacturers and operators for activities such as determining product requirements from customers (with operators acting as

direct customers of medical device manufacturers), gathering feedback, managing complaints, and reporting adverse events. These activities are part of legal obligations, including post-market surveillance and vigilance [6, 7], which highlights the critical role operators play in ensuring device safety and compliance. However, the current requirements are framed primarily from the perspective of manufacturers or service providers, offering limited guidance on the responsibilities of operators themselves.

Inter-stakeholder collaboration: The medical device industry forms an ecosystem involving multiple stakeholders who participate not only in manufacturing but also in the installation, operation, and servicing of devices, activities that require close collaboration. This interconnectedness is partially acknowledged in various clauses of the standard, such as the requirement for manufacturers to provide documented information to any external party or supplier responsible for installation activities (Clause 7.5.3) as well as for servicing activities (Clause 7.5.4). However, the standard does not fully capture the complexity of these interactions or provide clear mechanisms to support effective communication and coordination among all stakeholders. This limitation is also highlighted in the literature [17, 13], which notes that applying ISO 13485:2016 requirements in diverse healthcare settings, such as hospitals, can be challenging.

5 Improvement Paths

Acknowledging that ISO 13485:2016 provides valuable and comprehensive requirements for the design and development process for manufacturers, Section 4 highlights a set of limitations in its current form. This section presents potential approaches for improving the clarity and applicability of the standard, given that it is a requirements standard against which organizations can be certified. It does not aim to provide concrete solutions, as addressing such issues would require extensive collaboration among the experts of the technical committees responsible for advancing the standard, which is beyond the scope of this study.

As noted previously, the standard in its current form is well-suited for manufacturers in initiating, establishing, and managing the design and development process of medical devices. The first and most important decision, guiding the future of the standard, is the related to scope definition. It is important to recognize that defining the scope involves two distinct aspects: the applicable lifecycle stages and the applicable stakeholders. This distinction is necessary because, even for manufacturers, the standard does not address all stages of the lifecycle, such as decommissioning and disposal.

Currently, a discrepancy exists between the standard's formally "defined scope" and its "effective scope", which refers to the range of activities it actually addresses. The defined scope is significantly broader than what the standard's requirements currently cover. This inconsistency manifests in two key areas: the incomplete treatment of the product lifecycle and the restrictions on non-manufacturer stakeholders discussed in

Section 4. Consequently, the normative requirements in the main body of the standard do not fully align with the breadth of activities encompassed by its stated scope.

In order to fully understand the following suggestions, it is useful to clearly distinguish between the “defined scope” and the “effective scope” of the standard.

Defined scope The scope as stated in the introduction of the standard. It currently encompasses any organization involved in one or more stages of the medical device lifecycle—from design and development through disposal—independent of the organization’s specific role within that lifecycle.

Effective scope The scope as expressed through the requirements in the main body of the standard. It currently applies primarily to manufacturers and focuses on activities related to the design, production, and quality management of medical devices (see Figure 1).

In the following sections, these terms are referenced in quotation marks to indicate their specific meaning.

5.1 Scope Alignment by Stakeholder and Lifecycle Stages Restriction

The first, most straightforward and simplest approach for improvement would be to narrow the “defined scope” of the standard with respect to both the relevant stakeholders and medical device lifecycle stages, such that it fully matches the “effective scope”.

Based on this change, the intended audience, as specified in the “defined scope”, should be explicitly limited to manufacturers, thereby aligning it with the activities and processes reflected in the main body of the standard. Likewise, the relevant lifecycle stages detailed in the “defined scope” should be restricted to Governance and Planning, Product Realization, and Evaluation and Improvement, as these are the stages currently addressed by the requirements of the standard (see Figure 1). While the content of the standard would largely remain unchanged, apart from its introduction, explicitly redefining the scope in this way would make the content fully relevant and directly applicable to the defined stages and target audience, thus enhancing its usefulness and practical value. By narrowing the scope, the standard would also avoid potential ambiguities that may arise when applied outside its intended context. Manufacturers would benefit from clearer guidance tailored to the stages in which they are most actively involved, ensuring that the requirements are practical and actionable, while non-manufacturers would not try to enforce vague requirements based on an ill-defined scope. Furthermore, focusing the standard in this manner would facilitate its adoption and implementation, as organizations would be able to directly map the provisions to their processes without unnecessary interpretation. Overall, this adjustment represents a simple yet effective means to increase the standard’s relevance, usability, and impact within its intended context.

Restricting the scope in this way could also enable the development of a family of ISO 13485 standards for the medical device industry, analogous to the ISO/IEC 27001 family of standards for information security management, with other stakeholders or lifecycle

stages addressed in separate ISO 13485–based standards. The medical device industry has evolved significantly, particularly with the growth of digital health technologies and the Internet of Things (IoT), creating a complex ecosystem of stakeholders with diverse backgrounds and requirements. These developments have introduced new regulatory, technical, and operational challenges, as devices increasingly rely on software, connectivity, and data integration across multiple systems. As a result, stakeholders such as service providers, operators, and data managers play a critical role in ensuring device safety, performance, and compliance, yet their responsibilities are not fully addressed in the current ISO 13485:2016 framework. This complexity underscores the need for a more modular or tiered approach to standardization, where specific standards or extensions can target distinct stakeholders and lifecycle stages, enabling more precise guidance and clearer pathways for compliance across the entire medical device ecosystem.

Based on the limitations identified in Section 4, the proposed approach effectively addresses the key issues. By narrowing the scope, the approach ensures a complete representation of the lifecycle, as all relevant stages are now clearly defined. With the scope explicitly restricted, no processes or activities are overlooked. Concerns regarding the compliance of non-manufacturers and the role of operators are eliminated, as the standard applies exclusively to manufacturers. Inter-stakeholder collaboration is addressed to the extent that manufacturers are required to interact with other stakeholders; additional bilateral collaboration is unnecessary, as the standard focuses solely on the manufacturers’ perspective.

5.2 Scope Alignment by Stakeholder Retention and Lifecycle Restriction

A second, more demanding, yet balanced, path for improvement would be to restrict the medical device lifecycle stages included in the “defined scope” to those currently addressed by the “effective scope”, while maintaining the existing stakeholders within the “defined scope”.

Based on this change, the lifecycle stages specified in the “defined scope” should be explicitly limited to Governance and Planning, Product Realization, and Evaluation and Improvement, thereby aligning them with the “effective scope” reflected in the current requirements. At the same time, the intended audience defined in the “defined scope” would remain unchanged, continuing to encompass all organizations involved in one or more stages of the medical device lifecycle, irrespective of their specific role (see Figure 1). This approach would require a substantial extension of the main body of the standard, which currently addresses primarily manufacturers, as the requirements would need to be expanded to consistently address the needs of all stakeholders within the defined medical device lifecycle stages. Unlike the previous approach, this refinement strikes a balance between maintaining the existing lifecycle stages and updating the content to include specific requirements for the “newly identified” stakeholders. This can be achieved either by structuring the standard around stakeholders and addressing the relevant lifecycle stages for each, or by structuring it around lifecycle stages and specifying the stakeholders involved at each stage. Explicitly redefining the scope in this way ensures that the content corresponds to the specified lifecycle stages and target

audience, avoiding the broad interpretations and indirect connections that are currently necessary to satisfy the requirements. As a result, these adjustments improve both the structural clarity of the document and its overall utility for the medical device industry as a whole, since effective collaboration among the various stakeholders must be carefully considered when their processes and activities are described within the same document; otherwise, this complex stakeholder interplay cannot function properly.

With the inclusion of additional stakeholders, particular attention should be given to Clause 7, “Product Realization”, since, unlike the other clauses that based on their titles may appear relevant to multiple stakeholders, Clause 7 is primarily geared toward manufacturers. At the same time, it addresses activities relevant not only to manufacturers but also to non-manufacturer stakeholders, including Clause 7.2.3 on communication, Clause 7.5.3 on installation, and Clause 7.5.4 on servicing. The current structure is also problematic because servicing is nested under Clause 7.5, which primarily addresses production and associated services, potentially creating confusion regarding its intended scope. Communication, installation, and servicing should each be addressed in separate clauses, independent of product realization. For manufacturers, these activities occur during product realization, whereas for other stakeholders, they take place post-manufacturing. Separating these activities would clarify the roles and responsibilities of all stakeholders and enhance the standard’s overall applicability. In other words, reorganizing the standard to disentangle this content from the overarching Clause 7 would provide non-manufacturing organizations with clearer guidance on their roles within the medical device industry in the context of the standard.

Specifically for communication, as currently written, Clause 7.2.3 focuses narrowly on the exchange of product information between the manufacturer and the customer. In practice, communication requirements should encompass all stakeholders involved in the medical device lifecycle and clearly define the type of information to be exchanged, the frequency of exchange, and the roles and responsibilities of each party for both internal and external communications. Such a process would cover, for example, the dissemination of instructions for use from manufacturers to customers, repair manuals from manufacturers to service providers, and the reporting of adverse events or complaints from customers or operators to manufacturers. Including explicit requirements for how each stakeholder should handle, retain, and communicate this information would support more consistent and effective collaboration across the ecosystem, particularly given that certain types of information, such as post-market surveillance data or adverse event reports, are also legal obligations that must be communicated properly. It is important to note that this proposed communication process is distinct from the complaint handling and adverse event reporting requirements of Clause 8.2, which address these activities solely from the manufacturer’s perspective.

Based on the limitations identified in Section 4, this proposed approach effectively addresses the key issues. By narrowing the scope with respect to the lifecycle, the approach ensures a complete representation, as all relevant stages are now clearly defined. With the lifecycle scope explicitly restricted, no processes or activities are overlooked. Concerns regarding the compliance of non-manufacturers and the role of operators are eliminated, as the standard’s stakeholder scope is extended and now applies to them as

well, rather than exclusively to manufacturers. Furthermore, inter-stakeholder collaboration is enhanced through the communication clause, which specifies the exchange of information among all relevant parties.

5.3 Scope Alignment by Stakeholder and Lifecycle Stages Extension

Finally, the most comprehensive approach would require a holistic overhaul of the standard to align the “effective scope” with the ambitious breadth already articulated in the “defined scope”. This option would demand substantial effort and expert knowledge across multiple domains. The following lines present the general concept intended to serve as a starting point for any future extensions of the standard.

Based on this change, the requirements of the standard should be expanded to explicitly address all stakeholders specified in the “defined scope”, including not only manufacturers but also other organizations involved in one or more stages of the medical device lifecycle, such as suppliers, distributors, and service providers. Likewise, the requirements should be extended to comprehensively cover all lifecycle stages referenced in the “defined scope”, including Pre-Production Activities, Production, Post-Production Activities, and End-of-Life, ensuring that each stage receives adequate normative guidance (see Figure 1). This approach would transform ISO 13485 into a truly comprehensive quality management system standard that governs the entire medical device ecosystem across all lifecycle stages, thereby fulfilling the promise of its currently stated scope.

To illustrate how such an extension could be realized in practice, insights from the conducted case studies provide a concrete example. Building on these results, an effective solution involved extending the medical device lifecycle shown in Figure 1 to incorporate post-production processes and activities, thereby establishing a roadmap for non-manufacturing stakeholders, as illustrated in Figure 3. The resulting lifecycle represents an integration of Figures 1 and 3.

This extension is informed by the lifecycle framework presented in IEC 80001-1:2021 [8], a standard widely adopted by medical device operators and integrators. The standard defines general requirements for organizations to implement risk management before, during, and after connecting a health IT system to a health IT infrastructure. It emphasizes the maintenance of safety, effectiveness, and security while ensuring the engagement of relevant stakeholders throughout the process. It is important to note that the extension presented in Figure 3 is intended for illustrative purposes only and does not represent a recommended or authoritative lifecycle by the authors. Rather, it serves as a suggested approach highlighting a possible path for extending the lifecycle described in ISO 13485:2016. Adopting this extension allows coverage of the entire lifecycle, incorporation of processes relevant to non-manufacturing stakeholders, and support for inter-stakeholder collaboration across the various processes as needed. While this suggested timeline provides a starting point, identifying the specific processes and activities to include, as well as refining their sequencing and interactions, is beyond the scope of this work and remains a task for the relevant ISO technical committee in the future. Viewing the complete lifecycle illustrated in Figure 3 highlights the substantial disparity between the stated scope of ISO 13485:2016 and its actual coverage. Providing a compre-

Figure 3: Extended medical device lifecycle incorporating post-production processes and activities. This version highlights the roadmap and corresponding processes and activities for non-manufacturing stakeholders, complementing the original lifecycle shown in Figure 1. The approach is informed by the lifecycle framework presented in IEC 80001-1:2021. This figure is intended for illustrative purposes only and does not represent a recommended or authoritative lifecycle.

hensive framework of quality management requirements across the entire medical device lifecycle would require extensive additions to the current standard, demonstrating that, in its present form, it falls significantly short of this objective.

Based on the limitations identified in Section 4, this option effectively addresses all key issues. By fully extending the scope with respect to both lifecycle stages and stakeholders, the standard achieves a complete representation of the medical device ecosystem, encompassing all relevant stakeholders and lifecycle phases. With the lifecycle scope fully expanded, all associated processes and activities are explicitly included. Concerns regarding the compliance of non-manufacturers and the role of operators are eliminated, as the stakeholder scope of the standard is extended to apply to these actors as well, rather than exclusively to manufacturers. Furthermore, inter-stakeholder collaboration is comprehensively addressed, since the standard would include requirements applicable to all relevant parties, potentially supplemented by additional provisions within a communication clause similar to that described in Section 5.1.

6 Discussion

This work presents a set of shortcomings in ISO 13485:2016, identified as a secondary outcome of a series of case studies conducted within a Horizon Europe research project (see Section 4). It also describes possible routes for addressing these shortcomings, which differ in implementation difficulty and in scope with respect to medical device stakeholder

involvement and medical device lifecycle coverage (see Section 5). A key contribution of this work is the proposal of an extended medical device lifecycle, presented in Figure 3 and discussed in Section 5.3. These shortcomings were not the primary goal of the project but emerged in the course of collaboration among various medical device stakeholders. Given that medical devices constitute an ecosystem of products and services, it is important to disseminate findings that can enhance communication and collaboration among stakeholders, ultimately improving the ecosystem as a whole. At the same time, it should be acknowledged that ISO 13485:2016 is approaching a decade since its publication and that systematic updates are increasingly warranted. While the standard provides a comparatively clear and coherent framework, particularly when contrasted with the complexity and interpretive challenges of certain national and regional medical device regulations such as MDD and MDR, its age underscores the need for targeted evolution to better reflect current technological, organizational, and regulatory realities.

As the standard is intended to support organizations in establishing a quality management system, it provides an appropriate framework, more precisely a suitable medium, for addressing processes and activities across the entire medical device lifecycle, given that quality in both products and services is expected to be pervasive throughout that lifecycle. The proposed directions are not comprehensive, nor are they intended to be. It is acknowledged that extensive inter-stakeholder collaboration is required to define state-of-the-art content for a standards document, particularly one that specifies requirements against which organizations may be certified. The purpose of this contribution is therefore limited to outlining a small number of potential directions that could enhance the standard.

This work was initiated by medical device manufacturers, for whom ISO 13485:2016 already provides an effective framework. The motivation of the work was to explore how the standard could evolve to be equally applicable to the post-manufacturing phases of the medical device lifecycle. The purpose of the analysis is to outline several potential directions that could enhance the standard. An extensive overhaul of the standard is not advocated. Instead, the primary recommendation is to ensure that the defined scope is adequately and consistently covered.

7 Conclusion

The medical device industry relies on standards to deliver the life saving products and services it seeks to provide. ISO 13485:2016 is widely regarded as the benchmark standard for medical device manufacturers, and for good reason. Expanding its focus to better address the needs of non manufacturing medical device stakeholders could further enhance its value across the broader medical device ecosystem. This work advocates for an update to the standard by outlining a set of alternative approaches that vary in scope and level of change. These approaches range from a limited revision to the introductory sections, with the core requirements remaining largely unchanged, to a comprehensive revision that would transform the standard into a quality framework applicable to all medical device stakeholders across all stages of the medical device lifecycle. Further-

more, this discussion may inform and support the development of a broader family of ISO 13485 based standards, each tailored to the needs of different stakeholder groups operating at distinct stages of the medical device lifecycle.

8 Competing interests

The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

9 Grant information

This work has been performed as part of the NEMECYS project, supported in part by the European Commission Horizon Europe programme, grant number 101094323 and the UK Research and Innovation (UKRI) Horizon Europe funding guarantee under grant numbers 10065802, 10050933 and 10061304, and the Swiss State Secretariat for Education, Research and Innovation (SERI).

10 Acknowledgments

During the preparation of this manuscript, the authors used LLM-based tools for the purposes of supporting the structuring, editing, and language refinement of the text, to improve clarity, readability and consistency. All material in this manuscript, including the ideas and discussions, without exception, is the result of human expertise and collaborative effort. The authors have reviewed and edited all content and take full responsibility for the accuracy and integrity of this publication. Figures have been designed using resources from flaticon.com

References

- [1] Christos Androutsos et al. “MDCG 2019-16 Guidelines: Case Study-Based Assessment and Path Forward”. In: *European Interdisciplinary Cybersecurity Conference*. Springer. 2025, pp. 338–355.
- [2] Angelo Antonini et al. “Toward objective monitoring of Parkinson’s disease motor symptoms using a wearable device: wearability and performance evaluation of PDMonitor”. In: *Frontiers in neurology* 14 (2023), p. 1080752.
- [3] Mirka Buist and Max Ortiz-Catalan. “Engineering a Quality Management System for Academic Research: Navigating Challenges to Comply with the New Medical Device Regulations in Europe”. In: *Medical Devices: Evidence and Research* (2025), pp. 137–147.
- [4] Sergio Di Molfetta et al. “An overview of the FreeStyle Libre monitoring system for individuals with type 1 and type 2 diabetes”. In: *Expert Review of Medical Devices* 22.5 (2025), pp. 425–436.

- [5] European Union. “Council Directive 93/42/EEC of 14 June 1993 concerning medical devices”. In: *Official Journal of the European Union* L 169 (June 1993), pp. 1–43. URL: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/dir/1993/42/oj/eng>.
- [6] European Union. “Regulation (EU) 2017/745 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 5 April 2017 on medical devices”. In: *Official Journal of the European Union* L 117 (Apr. 2017), pp. 1–175. URL: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/reg/2017/745/oj/eng>.
- [7] European Union. “Regulation (EU) 2017/746 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 5 April 2017 on in vitro diagnostic medical devices”. In: *Official Journal of the European Union* L 117 (Apr. 2017), pp. 176–332. URL: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/reg/2017/746/oj/eng>.
- [8] International Electrotechnical Commission (IEC). *IEC 80001-1:2021 – Application of risk management for IT-networks incorporating medical devices – Part 1: Safety, effectiveness and security in the implementation and use of connected medical devices or connected health software*. Standard IEC 80001-1:2021. Geneva, Switzerland: International Electrotechnical Commission (IEC), 2021. URL: <https://www.iso.org/standard/72026.html>.
- [9] International Organization for Standardization (ISO). *ISO 13485:2016 – Medical devices – Quality management systems – Requirements for regulatory purposes*. Standard ISO 13485:2016. Geneva, Switzerland: International Organization for Standardization (ISO), 2016. URL: <https://www.iso.org/standard/59752.html>.
- [10] International Organization for Standardization (ISO). *ISO 13485:2016 Medical devices – Practical Guide*. Practical Guide. Geneva, Switzerland: International Organization for Standardization (ISO), 2017. URL: <https://www.iso.org/publication/PUB100422.html>.
- [11] International Organization for Standardization (ISO). *The Integrated Use of Management System Standards (IUMSS)*. Handbook. Geneva, Switzerland: International Organization for Standardization (ISO), 2018. URL: <https://www.iso.org/publication/PUB100435.html>.
- [12] International Organization for Standardization (ISO) and International Electrotechnical Commission (IEC). *ISO/IEC Directives, Part 1 – Procedures for the technical work – Consolidated ISO Supplement*. Tech. rep. ISO/IEC Directives, Part 1: V01/2024. Geneva, Switzerland: International Organization for Standardization (ISO) and International Electrotechnical Commission (IEC), 2024. URL: <https://www.iso.org/sites/directives/current/consolidated>.
- [13] Usman Iqbal, Peter Lachman, and Phillip Phan. *From compliance to excellence: how can ISO 13485 standards transform quality, safety, and innovation in medical devices?* 2025.
- [14] Martin Gilje Jaatun et al. “Nemecys: addressing challenges to building security into connected medical devices”. In: *Procedia Computer Science* 239 (2024), pp. 1361–1368.

- [15] Peter WJ Linders. “Setting standards: ISO 13485: challenges in achieving high-level structure compliance”. In: *Biomedical instrumentation & technology* 54.1 (2020), pp. 68–70.
- [16] Harald Noddeland et al. “A novel wearable bioimpedance sensor for continuous monitoring of fluid balance: a study on isotonic hypovolemia in healthy adults”. In: *Journal of Clinical Monitoring and Computing* 39.2 (2025), pp. 379–391.
- [17] Diego Augusto de Jesus Pacheco, Samuel Vinícius Bonato, and William Linck. “Advancing quality management in the medical devices industry: strategies for effective ISO 13485 implementation”. In: *International Journal for Quality in Health Care* 37.1 (2025), mzaf004.
- [18] Qingnan Sun et al. “A dual mode adaptive basal-bolus advisor based on reinforcement learning”. In: *IEEE journal of biomedical and health informatics* 23.6 (2018), pp. 2633–2641.